

Ports Past and Present

Records and Research Data Management Plan

Version 4.1

Reviewed and updated

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Introduction

This data management plan was composed for the Ports, Past and Present (PPP) project, in line with FAIR data principles. It is based on the core requirements for data management plans, as set out in the *Science Europe Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management*. The aim of this document is to establish robust data management for PPP throughout its lifetime. Transparent and consistent data management structure will ensure that all project data, where appropriate, is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) and that all records generated during this project will be managed in line with UCC Records management policy and the criteria defined by WEFO. It will also minimise the risks of data loss, accidental data misuse, version confusion and duplication of work.

All audit trail documentation will be stored and made available in electronic format. Irish partners will comply with the Electronic Commerce Act 2000 with regard to electronic storage and location of documents. Welsh partners will comply with the UK equivalent, see: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/the-ecommerce-directive-and-the-uk>).

This plan ensures that all audit trail documentation will be made available to the European Commission and European Court of Auditors upon request in accordance with Article 140(1) of Regulation (EU) No 1303/2013.

1. Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

a. How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?

Data will be collected in the course of almost all project work; in particular, internal and external evaluation, income and expenditure, historical research, social research, meetings, and publicity & communications.

New data will be collected from project partners, stakeholders, supported enterprises and participants; through surveys and questionnaires, event sign-up, social media analysis, consolidation of financial and employment information. New data will be produced through recruitment and employment, meetings, publicity and communications, and project activities. Software used will include the Microsoft Office suite (Teams, SharePoint, Forms, Word, Excel), Adobe, SurveyMonkey, Mailchimp (for newsletter) WordPress (for project website), Omeka (for management and visualisation of archival and heritage data) and social media platforms (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook).

Existing data will be collected in the course of external evaluation and through historical research. It may also form part of internal evaluation. This data will be collected through archival research, literature research, social media / website research, census analysis, report reading.

Data provenance will be maintained by maintaining versions and naming according to the versions. In the case of historical / research data, contextual information may accompany the data in an additional document or metadata fields (the latter in the case of Omeka). This could include: date of saving, where sourced, who owns the content and sharing rights.

b. What data (for example the kinds, formats, and volumes) will be collected or produced?

Broadly speaking, data can be divided into records of the research project and research data. Records of the research project include financial data, back-up documents, project plans & reports, external evaluation data, and internal evaluation data. Research data includes backups of research materials for project research and project delivery outputs. Records will be kept in line with the project retention schedule and research data will be made FAIR where possible and appropriate.

Financial data will be collected for the financial claim and MVT checks: invoices, expense claims, payslips, bank transactions and receipts.

Back-up documents will be collected as supporting evidence of project activity and expenditure: photographs, meeting minutes, agendas and notes, itineraries and schedules, posters. Employment and recruitment data will be collected: employment contracts, secondment letters, timesheets. Back-up documents will likely take up significant volume throughout the project lifespan, as they will accumulate alongside project activity. These documents will vary in formats: .jpeg, .xlsx, .pdf, and .docx.

Project plans and reports will be created and saved in various versions; this data will be limited in volume but will need careful version control. Plans and reports will mainly be in .docx format.

Much of the above data will be provided to WEFO for use “by WEFO, the Managing Authority and the European Commission to monitor programme progress, for verifications of claims and for research and evaluation purposes” ([WEFO Guidance on Monitoring and Evaluation](#), 2016).

Research data may include secondary reports, journal articles and essays, as well as archival content: maps, photographs, video content, first-hand accounts, interview transcripts, and historical records. It may also include tabular metadata in .csv format. The level of detail provided in this plan will increase as data collection continues, with further specifications provided by the researchers doing data collection.

External evaluation data may include specifications (in various versions), procurement contracts and performance monitoring, photographs, visitor / footfall statistics, questionnaire and survey forms (in various versions, as well as completed forms), participant details, and secondary research material.

Internal evaluation data may include photographs, reports, financial analysis data, questionnaire and survey forms (in various versions, as well as completed forms), participant details, supported enterprise information, and secondary research material. These documents will vary in formats: .jpeg, .xlsx, .pdf, and .docx.

Project delivery outputs could include documentary video clips, commissioned artwork, community publications, creative content for apps, and leaflets. These may be in physical form and/or in .jpeg, .pdf, and .docx formats. Physical artwork storage will be decided based on type and location, taking due consideration to security.

2. Documentation and data quality

a. What metadata and documentation (for example the methodology of data collection and way of organising data) will accompany the data?

Data will be organised into folders on Microsoft Teams.

Naming should be descriptive and follow the following convention:

YYYYMMDD Document type Version

Eg: 20191212 Data Management Plan v.1

Versions should be controlled through naming Version 1, 2, etc (in the case of relatively significant changes) and sub-divided for minor edits, to Version 1.1, 1.2 etc. This should allow for multiple versions in one location but show clearly which version is the most recent.

Folders should be structured as follows:

Team folder -> Work package-> [activity sub-folder if needed]

Financial data should be shared to the partner-specific Teams so that only relevant team members working on the claim can access this potentially sensitive material.

Less folders are preferable, to allow for data discoverability. Where needed, individual pieces of data should be accompanied by clear information on location of sourcing, ownership and sharing rights.

New research data will be created and collected as part of the project. This will include:

1. archival material, e.g. text, pictures, pre-existing historic films of ports etc;
2. oral history interviews with members of port communities;
3. potential interviews with community groups, heritage groups etc. already working on port heritage;
4. metadata using the [Dublin Core](#) expanded schema generated by Omeka Content Management System.

In all cases, metadata will be produced for each individual file on Omeka in the form of a .csv file. The creation of metadata for each file will help the various individuals working on PPP to be able readily to access relevant information to support the different outputs and outcomes.

The metadata will comprise of a range of different file characteristics. Indicative information might include: date of collection; type of information/source (e.g. oral history interview, archival source); location referred to; relevant time period; important themes arising. Metadata will be captured in the Dublin Core schema and Captured in the DC metadata and shared in an interoperable format via .csv tabular data.

b. What data quality control measures will be used?

Subject-matter experts will be leading and participating in the project on the research side, ensuring quality of data produced and collected. A spreadsheet validation process will be implemented for .csv tabular data, quality control for images (metadata, naming conventions, image quality) will be introduced and the project will use a consistent taxonomy of keywords and definitions based on Library of Congress [standardised](#)

[vocabularies and authorities](#). Further quality control measures will be implemented during the life-cycle of the project based on demand.

The Project Manager will have an overview of shared folders and data collection, and will monitor the data on an ongoing basis – with the assistance of the Research Support Officer and Postdoctoral Researchers. The Project Manager will maintain compliance with EU guidelines and GDPR, adhering to Regulation (EU) No 1303/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of the European Union. The project manager will also incorporate any feedback from WEFO's MVT checks into data management. The project will ensure adherence to copyright and maintain reliable sourcing through maintaining records of source information and sharing rights, where applicable.

3. Storage and backup during the research process

a. How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

Data will be stored on devices synced to Microsoft Teams storage, which is backed up by SharePoint software. The Omeka content management system is hosted on a UCC virtual machine with weekly redundant backups, and also serves as a storage and backup repository for project data. Partner-level data will be stored in their own secure digital locations and transfer may be carried out for non-financial data to the lead beneficiary at project end.

b. How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

In terms of finance data, partner finance offices will ensure that electronic copies (PDFs) of invoices are kept with supporting bank statements. The following are the Financial and HR systems used by partners and which will be underpinning financial controls and operations on this project: UCC: Agresso and Core HR, Wexford County Council: Integra and Core HR, UWTSD: bluQube and HERA system, Aberystwyth: Agresso Finance and HR.

Personal data – from partners, stakeholders or project participants – will be stored securely, with consent, on Teams cloud software and in secure partner data locations. Confidentiality and privacy will be considered throughout data management.

All beneficiaries are fully compliant with respective general data protection regulations: the EU-GDPR (applicable to Irish partners) and the UK-GDPR (applicable to Welsh partners). Data protection will be guided by UCC's [Data Protection Policy](#) and Record Management Policy. In line with the latter policy, any records or data will be processed "in a manner that safeguards and protects the integrity, confidentiality and availability of the data at all times." In line with WEFO rules, data will exclusively be used for research / claim purposes and no identifiable data will be published without explicit consent from the individual.

Risks involved in handling sensitive data include: a) a data breach; b) revealing data to the public / another group without adequate permissions; c) non-compliance with GDPR. These risks will be mitigated against by taking the respective actions: a) minimising personal data gathered, limiting to what is necessary, maintaining

secure data storage with restricted access, anonymising personal data; b) securing all necessary sharing rights and permissions and tracking same alongside data; c) ensuring all team members understand GDPR guidelines, and follow institutional policies which are aligned with GDPR. In the event of a data breach, PPP will immediately inform WEFO via our Project Development Officer.

4. Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

a. If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

The project beneficiaries will ensure compliance with GDPR throughout the project lifespan. Stakeholders and other project participants may be asked to provide some minimal personal data. Explicit and informed consent will be secured for these individuals, and they will be provided with a data protection notice.

Their data will be anonymised wherever possible; non-anonymised personal data will be stored securely. Most personal data relating to external project participants will be redacted or destroyed at project end – except where their consent explicitly allows otherwise (for example, in the case of film participants, and named oral history interviewees). The external evaluation supplier will be instructed to ensure GDPR compliance in handling personal data.

Each external participant in the project providing personal data - such as stakeholders, community groups or creative practitioners - will be presented with a data consent form informing them about the project, how we collect personal data and their rights according to GDPR rules. The consent form will vary in complexity depending on the data it relates to.

b. How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Data will be made openly accessible wherever possible – except in the case where permission and usage rights do not allow it.

Intellectual property rights and ownership will be managed as specified in the Collaboration Agreement signed by all partners. Per the collaboration agreement, “All right and title to, and interest in, any and all Foreground generated during the project solely by the Personnel of one Party shall vest and remain vested in such Party. All right and title to, and interest in, any and all Foreground generated jointly by the Personnel of two or more of the Parties (“Joint Foreground”) shall vest and remain vested in the Parties concerned in the ratio of their respective inventive percentage contributions to the generation of that Foreground.” Per these ownership rights as set out in the agreement, permission may need to be sought from project partners to make available their owned content.

Copyright and permission restrictions may apply in the case of third-party data. While the project will endeavour to secure full and open dissemination rights for content, there may be instances where conditions

of use place restrictions or disallow re-use. Rights conditions will be made clear wherever project data is shared in such a way as it may be re-used.

The project will align with UCC's Record Management Policy, which states that "recognition is given to the University's obligations as a data controller and processor towards data subjects under the University's Data Protection Policy and Data Protection legislation, and to the special and limited derogations given under that legislation for processing data for research and statistical purposes, and for archival purposes in the public interest."

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

a. How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

The project will follow the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary", in the context of sharing data. Research / archival data will be shared through a variety of means throughout the project:

- Publicity and communication (WP6); Tweets, Instagram posts, project website, journal articles, external events, conference presentations, leaflets, web-forums, e-newsletter.
- Community art meetings and sessions (WP2).
- Documentary films, five of which will be created under WP3.
- Graphic panels, apps (WP4)
- Community heritage meetings and sessions (WP5)
- Open project database, making data available for use under a license such as CC BY 4.0 International license.

It is envisioned that project plans and reports will be made directly available to interested parties using Zenodo towards the end of the project.

Where appropriate, data will be made available, at the latest, upon publication of findings. However, there may be delays in line with specific discipline best practice, or for protection of intellectual property. The data lifecycle and use of open data practices will be detailed in a peer reviewed essay in the [Journal of Open Humanities Data](#).

Usage rights for research data and content may vary depending on terms of use, particularly in the case of film and video content. Usage rights will be made clear to users. The project will endeavour to open access to content as much as possible, by paying due attention to securing full sharing rights during data collection, production and procurement. The data management plan takes its lead from the DARIAH [Open Access Toolkit](#) and the PARTHENOS project [guidelines for FAIRifying data management](#).

Research data will be preserved in the long-term by storage via Zenodo (select project plans and reports, other relevant outputs) and the Digital Repository of Ireland/ People's Collection Wales (cultural heritage data). Research records will be retained in the project archive in Teams/ SharePoint for as long as they are of continuing value to the researcher and the wider research community, and if applicable, as long as specified by

research funder (WEFO) patent law, legislative and other regulatory requirements. Time periods for retention will likely align with UCC’s [Records Retention Schedule for Research](#); please see table below.

b. How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term (for example a data repository or archive)?

Data will be retained or destroyed based on the guidelines in UCC’s Record Management Policy. This exceeds the document retention requirements of WEFO, which requires a retention period until, at least 2026. Selection of data will be subject to WEFO guidance, as well as further consideration in the project closure period. In line with GDPR, some personal data may need to be redacted (including most personal data from project participants, depending on details of their consent).

The UCC Record Management Policy guides retention as follows (adjusted to remove non-applicable information):

Correspondence, working papers, research notes	Retain until no longer required for reference or administrative use, then destroy.
Proposal-related forms, protocols, applications, reports, minutes.	Retain 7 years after conditions relating to the proposal have been satisfied.
Records relating to non-competitive and/or discretionary fund allocation.	Retain minimum of 7 years after action completed, then destroy.
Final reports	Retain 10 years after conditions relating to the proposal have been satisfied. Required as University archives.
All other reports -- for example progress reports.	Retain minimum of 7 years after conditions relating to the proposal have been satisfied, then destroy.
Contracts and agreements for use of the final product/research outcomes.	Retain until all conditions of the contract or agreement have been met. Required as University Archives.
Project Records	Retain 10 years after action completed. Required as University archives.
Research Data	Made FAIR where possible. Retained indefinitely in Digital repository of Ireland/ People’s Collection Wales (cultural heritage data) and Zenodo (select project plans and reports, other relevant outputs). Subject to conditions of consent from participants, where applicable.
Web Content	The project will guard against link rot in its publications and materials by using perma.cc . The website will be snapshotted incrementally on perma.cc, serving as an additional redundant form of backup for web content.

	Retain indefinitely. Files from perma.cc will be archived on Zenodo as .wacz web archive files.
Records relating to consultancy jobs where the tender/expressions of interest etc was successful and the required service were provided.	Retain minimum of 7 years after all terms and conditions of the contract completed then destroy.
Records relating to consultancy jobs where the tender/expressions of interest etc was unsuccessful or where the required service was not provided.	Retain minimum of 7 years after all terms and conditions of the contract completed then destroy.
Records relating to the provision of services.	Retain minimum of 7 years after all terms and conditions of the contract completed then destroy.

Additional retention detail in advance of project closure

Audit trail (financial) University College Cork	10 years post project end
Audit trail (human resources records) University College Cork	10 years post project end
Back up material for indicators, CCTs all project	10 years post project end
Audit trail (financial) Aberystwyth University	2027 minimum and will only destroy on WEFO confirmation that no longer needed
Audit trail (human resources records) Aberystwyth University	2027 minimum and will only destroy on WEFO confirmation that no longer needed
Audit trail (financial) CAWCS	Pending confirmation; until 2026 at a minimum as required by WEFO
Audit trail (human resources records) CAWCS	Pending confirmation; until 2026 at a minimum as required by WEFO
Audit trail (financial) Wexford County Council	Pending confirmation; until 2026 at a minimum as required by WEFO
Audit trail (human resources records) Wexford County Council	Pending confirmation; until 2026 at a minimum as required by WEFO

Foreseeable future users of heritage and research data could include a) Stakeholders and members of the ports communities, b) academic researchers, c) The Tourism Network created as part of PPP, along with individual tourism boards/advertisers, d) members of the entertainment industry (film / television) and e) history enthusiasts or other generally interested parties.

It's envisioned that much heritage research and archival data will be shared throughout the project lifespan – albeit in curated forms. For example, stories from the ports may be re-told via an app, signage, creative work and / or a community workshop. Both the curated forms of the data and the original data will be maintained at project close, and as much as possible of this data will be shared.

The app, signage, creative work, and website will be maintained wherever possible. Minimal maintenance responsibilities will likely be handed to members of the tourism network established during the project. Open and easy-to-use technology will be used for these platforms as much as possible throughout project delivery.

Foreseeable future users of contracts, plans, procedures and financial records would mainly be the partner institutions as well as WEFO, for purposes of evaluation, audit, and organisational record-keeping. The project will co-ordinate with all to determine potential use needs..

Zenodo will be used for data storage and data sharing after project close. Storage will need to be guaranteed for at least five years. The project will use [Science Europe's Criteria for the Selection of Trustworthy Repositories](#).

If research data and records are to be deleted or destroyed, either because the agreed period of retention has expired or for legal or ethical reasons, this will be done so in accordance with all legal, ethical, research funder and collaborator requirements and with particular concern for confidentiality and security. For any data that is to be destroyed, it will be done in accordance with these principles.

c. What methods or software tools will be needed to access and use the data?

The project files publicly archived in a Zenodo community will consist of .csv tabular data and PDFs. Both formats are FAIR principles compliant and will continue to be easily readable in the future. Any media-based data archived via SharePoint, the Digital Repository of Ireland and projects such as Europeana and the People's Collection of Wales will be in interoperable formats such as .jpeg, .png, .wav, .mp3 and .mp4. These formats will continue to be easily accessible and reusable by future users.

Any GDPR-relevant data archived within UCC in its role of data controller or confidential project data will need final review (integrated within closure plans) and a sustainability plan for secure access beyond the life cycle of the project, in line with ethical commitments to participants.

d. How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?

The data may be re-used in the context of academic research, academic writing, creative writing, entertainment (film / tv) and for tourism. Any identifiers therefore need to be broad enough to be employed by a range of users.

The project materials will be archived in a Zenodo community, providing each item with a DOI. Any additional items not suitable for Zenodo will be archived on Figshare, and will also have a DOI. Project web resources and website content is being archived using perma.cc, providing each archived item with a persistent identifier. Each item on the website uses the perma.cc link as its persistent identifier link in the Omeka metadata. Further plans are under discussion to archive selected datasets in the Digital Repository of Ireland and to aggregate them to Europeana and the People's Collection of Wales. These archives will also have persistent identifiers.

6. Data management responsibilities and resources

- a. Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

Responsibility for research data management lies primarily with Principal Investigators (PIs). For each work package, responsibility for implementing the data management plan will be delegated to the work package lead investigator. In practice, data management will be led by the Project Manager and the Postdoctoral Researchers at UCC, with the assistance of Project Coordinators at the partner institutions. Data management process and practice will be refined through the process of developing this plan. The Project Manager will have responsibility for this Data Management Plan and its development, ensuring it is revised and reviewed as needed.

- b. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

The project has not budgeted any finance against data management, but it will be incorporated into project overheads if required. It's estimated that data management work should take less than 5% of Project Manager, Project Co-ordinator and Postdoctoral Researcher time. Once a system is in place, maintenance should take minimal time.